

Marketing Problems and Prospects of Cottage Industries - A Study with Special Reference to Madurai District

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Introduction

Cottage industries, on the other hand also called household industries, are organized by individuals with private resources and with the help of family members and are pursued as full-time or part-time occupation. The capital investment is small and the equipments used are simple. These industries generally use locally available resources, raw materials and indigenous skills. The output produced in each industrial unit is generally sold in local market.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the Marketing problems and prospects of the selected units in the cottage industry like problems in selection of target market and market information
2. To suggest the appropriate strategies to improve the marketing of cottage industry products

Limitations of the Study

The study is confined to the cottage mills in Madurai district only.

Research Methodology

Geographical area covered	: Madurai District
Research Design	: Descriptive style
Data Source	: Both Primary and Secondary data
Sampling Unit	: Manager/owner of the cottage units
Research Instrument	: Interview schedule
Questionnaire Design	: Both open and closed ended questions

Analysis and Interpretation

Classification of cottage units based on the income

Classification of cottage units based on the income is an important aspect for this research. The cottage units are classified in to three categories such as less than 10 lakhs (LIU), 10 to 20 lakhs (MIU) and above 20 lakhs (HIU).

Variables Related to Selection of Target Market

Variables related to selection of target market among the respondents have been measured with the help of eight factors. One of the factors in marketing problems among the respondents is selection of target market. The respondents' perception on selection of target market has been measured with the help of five variables. The respondents are asked to rate these variables at five point scale according to their order of acceptance. The assigned scores are from 5 to 1 respectively. The mean score of variables in selection of target market among the LIU, MIU and HIU respondents have been measured separately and given in Table 1.1

Table 1.1 Variables in selection of target market among the respondents

S. No.	Variables in selection of target market	Mean Score among respondents in			F-statistics
		LIU	MIU	HIU	
1.	Insufficient information about the potentiality of market.	3.884	3.108	3.504	3.981*
2.	Lack of information regarding distribution of population according to age, sex, income, family size, education etc.	3.733	3.307	3.316	3.596*
3.	Lack of adequate knowledge about life style and personality of customers.	3.918	3.668	3.184	3.617*
4.	Lack of information about user's status, usage rate, benefits sought attitudes, etc.	3.814	3.891	3.796	0.991
5	Insufficient understanding and expertise of procedure of segmenting market.	4.067	3.499	3.107	4.266*
6	Unnecessary reliance on past experience and practices regarding the selection of market.	3.842	3.191	3.528	3.986*
7	Lack of appropriate data for measuring the efficacy of different markets.	3.723	3.292	3.969	3.284*
8	Lack of eagerness and enthusiasm in searching new and high potential markets.	3.703	3.412	3.225	3.523*

* Significant at five per cent level.

The highly viewed variable in selection of target market among the LIU respondents is insufficient understanding and expertise of procedure of segmenting market and lack of adequate knowledge about life style and personality of customers. Since their mean scores are 4.067 and 3.918 respectively. Among the MIU respondents, these are lack of information about user's status, usage rate, benefits sought attitudes, etc and lack of adequate knowledge about life style and personality of customers with the mean score of 3.891 and 3.668 respectively whereas among the HIU respondents, these two are lack of appropriate data for measuring the efficacy of different markets and Lack of information about user's status, usage rate, benefits sought attitudes, etc. of the cottage industries since their mean scores are 3.969 and 3.794 respectively. Regarding the view on the variables in the selection of target market, the significant difference among the three groups of respondents have been noticed in seven variables out of eight variables since their respective 'F' statistics are significant at five per cent level.

Variables in Selection of Target Market and its Reliability

In total, five variables have been included to measure the selection of target market among the respondents. The scores of the four variables in it have been included for the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to examine the reliability and validity of variables in it. The CFA results in standardized factor loading and its 't' statistics, composite reliability and average variance extracted. The overall reliability of the factor has been tested with the help of Cronbach Alpha. The results are given in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2 Reliability and Validity of Variables in target market

S.No.	Variables in target market	Standardized factor loading	't' statistics	Composite reliability	Average variance extracted
1.	Lack of adequate knowledge about life style and personality of customers	0.9138	7.339*	0.6639	55.64
2.	Insufficient understanding and expertise of procedure of segmenting market	0.8814	7.083*		
3.	Insufficient information about the potentiality of market.	0.8427	6.446*		
4.	Unnecessary reliance on past experience and practices regarding the selection of market.	0.7905	5.858*		
5.	Lack of information about user's status, usage rate, benefits sought attitudes, etc.	0.7382	5.517*		
6.	Lack of appropriate data for measuring the efficacy of different markets.	0.6713	5.261*		

7.	Lack of eagerness and enthusiasm in searching new and high potential markets.	0.6227	4.881*		
8.	Lack of information regarding distribution of population according to age, sex, income, family size, education etc.	0.5637	4.362*		

Cronbach alpha: 0.8110.

The included eight variables in selection of target market explain it to the extent of 81.10 per cent since its Cronbach Alpha is 0.8110. The standardized factor loadings of the variables in the selection of target market are greater than 0.60 which shows its content validity. The significance of ‘t’ statistics of the standardized factor loading of the variables in it shows the convergent validity. It is also proved by the composite reliability and average variance extracted since these are greater than its standard minimum of 0.50 and 50.00 per cent respectively. The analysis reveals that the included variables in selection of target market explain it to a reliable extent.

Table 1.3 Score on selection of target market (STM) among the Respondents

S.No.	Score on selection of target market	Mean scores among			Total
		LIU	MIU	HIU	
1.	Up to 2.00	32	17	14	63
2.	2.00–3.00	45	23	39	107
3.	3.01–4.00	86	48	30	164
4.	Above 4.00	26	37	20	83
	Total	189	125	103	417

*Significant at five per cent level.

The important score on selection of target market among the respondents are 3.01 to 4.00 and 2.00 to 3.00 which constitute 39.3 and 25.7 per cent to the total respectively. The important score on selection of target market among the LIU are 3.01 to 4.00 and 2.00–3.00 which constitute 45.05 and 23.81 per cent to the total respectively. Among the MIU, these are 3.01 to 4.00 and above 4.00 which constitute 38.4 and 29.6 per cent to the total respectively. Among the HIU, these are 2.00 to 3.00 and 3.01–4.00 which constitute 37.86 and 29.13 per cent to the total respectively. The analysis reveals that the level of perception on selection of target market among the LIU is higher than among the MIU and the HIU.

Variables Related to Market Information

Variables related to market information among the respondents have been measured with the help of nine variables. One of the factors in marketing problems among the respondents is market information. The respondents’ perception on market information has been measured with the help of nine variables. The respondents are asked to rate these variables at five point scale according to their order of acceptance. The assigned scores are from 5 to 1 respectively. The mean score of variables in market information among the LIU, MIU and HIU respondents have been measured separately and given in Table 1.4.

Table 1.4 Variables in market information among the respondents

S.No.	Variables in market information	Mean Score among respondents in			F-statistics
		LIU	MIU	HIU	
1.	Lake of getting the latest information	3.858	3.267	3.163	4.385*
2.	Lake of using modern technology	3.744	3.456	3.101	4.027*
3.	Lake of government related information	3.730	3.111	3.099	4.114*
4.	Lake of local agencies support	3.922	3.888	3.814	0.822
5	Lake of information about competitor	3.814	3.784	3.767	0.587
6	Lake of information about new design related to products, package etc	3.770	3.170	3.351	3.737*
7	Lake of information related to bank activities	3.197	3.247	3.211	0.831
8	Lake of Correct information on services	3.914	3.864	3.849	0.793
9	Error free records	3.827	3.856	3.909	1.014

* Significant at five per cent level.

The highly viewed variable in market information among the LIU respondents is Lake of local agencies support and Lake of correct information on services. Since their mean scores are 3.922 and 3.914 respectively. Among the MIU respondents, these are same with the mean score of 3.888 and 3.864 respectively whereas among the HIU respondents, these two are error free records and lake of local agencies support since their mean scores are 3.909 and 3.814 respectively. Regarding the view on the variables in marketing information, the significant difference among the three groups of respondents have been noticed in four variables out of nine variables since their respective 'F' statistics are significant at five per cent level.

Variables in Market Information and its Reliability

In total, nine variables have been included to measure the market information among the respondents. The scores of the nine variables in it have been included for the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to examine the reliability and validity of variables in it. The CFA results in standardized factor loading and its 't' statistics, composite reliability and average variance extracted. The overall reliability of the factor has been tested with the help of Cronbach Alpha. The results are given in Table 1.5.

Table 1.5 Reliability and Validity of Variables in market information

S.No.	Variables in market information	Standardized factor loading	't' statistics	Composite reliability	Average variance extracted
1.	Lake of local agencies support	0.9004	7.382*	0.8144	59.69
2.	Lake of Correct information on services	0.8856	6.914*		
3.	Lake of getting the latest information	0.8608	6.569*		
4.	Error free records	0.8347	6.192*		
5.	Lake of information about new design related to products, package etc	0.7932	5.781*		
6.	Lake of information about competitor	0.7611	5.286*		
7.	Lake of information related to bank activities	0.7527	4.819*		
8.	Lake of using modern technology	0.7162	4.637*		
9.	Lake of government related information	0.6816	4.268*		

Cronbach alpha: 0.8206

The included nine variables in market information explain it to the extent of 82.06 per cent since its Cronbach Alpha is 0.8206. The standardized factor loadings of the variables in market information are greater than 0.60 which shows its content validity. The significance of 't' statistics of the standardized factor loading of the variables in it shows the convergent validity. It is also proved by the composite reliability and average variance extracted since these are greater than its standard minimum of 0.50 and 50.00 per cent respectively. The analysis reveals that the included variables in market information explain it to a reliable extent.

Table 1.6 Score on market information (SMI) among the Respondents

S.No.	Score on Market Information	Mean Scores Among			Total
		LIU	MIU	HIU	
1.	Up to 2.00	27	15	16	58
2.	2.00–3.00	36	39	42	117
3.	3.01–4.00	59	42	28	129
4.	Above 4.00	67	29	17	113
	Total	189	125	103	417

*Significant at five per cent level.

The important score on market information among the respondents are 3.01 to 4.00 and 2.00 to 3.00 which constitute 30.9 and 28.1 per cent to the total respectively. The important score on market information among the LIU are above 4.00 and 3.01 to 4.00 which constitute 35.45 and 31.22 per cent to the total respectively. Among the MIU, these are 3.01 to 4.00 and 2.00 to 3.00 which constitute 33.6 and 31.2 per cent to the total respectively. Among the HIU, these are 2.00–3.00 and 3.01 to 4.00 which constitute 40.78 and 27.18 per cent to the total respectively. The analysis reveals that the level of perception on market information among the HIU is higher than among the MIU and the LIU.

Conclusion

Cottage Industries plays major role in the economic development of the country especially in India. But they face lot of marketing related problems especially in identification of target markets and collection of marketing information. So it is necessary to give training related to these aspects helps to develop their knowledge towards the above aspects and also helps to identify the target markets and collect the marketing information. This helps to improve their product marketability and also helps to enlarge their business.